

THE ROLE OF INTERNET OF THINGS FOR HEALTHY FISH AND ENVIRONMENT IN THE EUROPEAN AQUACULTURE

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Introduction

The overall objective of the project FutureEUAqua is to promote sustainable growth of environmental friendly organic and conventional aquaculture to meet future challenges of the growing consumer demand for high quality, nutritious and responsibly produced food. In WP5 of the FutureEUAqua project we are committed to develop and test a multiplatform tracking system for simultaneously monitoring the activity and physiology of fish, as well as the main parameters of the environment where they are farmed, by using a wireless communication system. The study of aquatic animals (e.g. fish behaviour, condition, physiology) and the farming environment presents unique challenges to scientists because of the physical characteristics of water. However, scientific studies and efforts have increasingly turned to the use of electronic sensors, which have enhanced our knowledge on the performances of the farmed fish and the impacts on the surrounding aquatic system. In their most basic form, electronic sensors and tags may include radio or acoustic beacons transmitting signals, which can bring specific codes to identify animals, and allow them to be tracked using receivers that detect the transmitted signals (Hazen et al. 2012). Basic archival tags must be, instead, physically recovered in order to obtain the data. Because the strength of radio signals rapidly attenuate in seawater, acoustic transmissions is preferred for fish tracking in marine environment (Lembo et al., 2002), while radio transmission is commonly used in freshwater environment. More advanced tags incorporate sensors that measure and record a suite of environmental and/or biological parameters of fish (Cooke et al. 2016). Simple biomass estimators and logging stations, installed on the feeding barge and/or on the cages, can give full control over all water parameters and provide the information required to monitor/expand the production. Flexible sensors systems are conceived to log oxygen, temperature, salinity, sea current, pH, wind and CO₂. In addition, sensor and camera systems may provide also information for estimating the biomass in the cages and developing reliable fish feeding strategies. Indeed, electronic sensors are significantly improving our understanding of fish behaviour and are emerging as key sources of information for improving aquaculture management practices. The wireless communication system to monitor the large scale demonstration activities foreseen in the project FutureEUAqua will both facilitate effective study design and replication, increasing the accuracy of data standardization, processing and interpretation (e.g., Huveneres et al. 2016), providing industry with the information needed to facilitate health/welfare and optimal management practices.

State of the art

A first step activity carried out in WP5 was the review of the state of the art and future needs in terms of technologies for fish tracking, environmental monitoring and biomass assessing. The most relevant technologies and methodologies are described below. Accelerometer pressure tags transmit 3D acceleration of fish as they move within the receiver array and also transmit depth data. This acceleration value can be used as a measure of activity of a free ranging animal in nature or captivity. Applications may include measuring swimming speed via tail beat acceleration, feeding events, spawning activity, nocturnal/diurnal activity and responses to changing oxygen, salinity and temperature in the environment. Electromyogram (EMG) transmitters measure muscle activity using probes inserted into the musculature of the fish. They provide a powerful quantitative estimate of the energetic costs associated with physical activity of fish. EMG values can be calibrated in terms of fish oxygen consumptions measured over periods of spontaneous activity or over the same times in swims of selected speeds and durations, by using a swimming chamber. This in turn allows to obtain quantitative estimates of the metabolic costs of activity of farmed fish. The bioenergetics of the target species (muscular activity patterns) can be modelled, based on fish mass and swimming speed, to predict the mass-specific standard metabolic rate (SMR), the active metabolic rate (AMR) and the scope for activity (SFA). The difference between AMR and SMR indicates the energetic expenditure available to support all locomotor and physiological activities (SFA). The oxygen consumption rate (MO₂) can be measured during exhaustive swimming trials (U_{crit}), carried out in swimming chambers, to estimate the energetic expenditure linked to the different swimming velocities. MO₂ can be further calibrated with the signals transmitted by the tailbeat accelerometer tags, as well as with the EMGs signal received via two pairs of wire electrodes surgically implanted in both the red and white muscle (Zupa et al., 2015). The calibration gives the possibility to correlate each single swimming level of the fish to the oxygen consumption rate (e.g. Carbonara et al., 2014). In this way, the activity based energetic expenditure can be assessed (i.e. the fish physiological status), as well as the relative cost of living for fish in their environment. Fish detection and size measurement using acoustic signals has been used in research to measure fish

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size of farmed fish, although with severe limitation due to how inaccurate these measurements inherently are. Also infrared (IR) beam technology has been utilized in aquaculture to detect the presence of fish and biomass estimation. The concept utilizes an IR emitter on one side and an IR receiver on the opposite side. When the fish pass between the two then the beam is interrupted and the receiver will register the appropriate event. Moreover, mention should be made of underwater stereo-video systems, which are capable of making accurate, non-invasive measurements of fish length by analysing the pair of simultaneously captured images.

A real-time wireless communication system and sensor network

A real time wireless communication system and sensor network will be tested during the large scale demonstration activities. The system architecture includes a family of compact, submersible environmental sensors (e.g. dissolved oxygen, temperature, salinity, turbidity, tilt, etc.) with underwater and in air wireless communications. A cloud-based platform will allow to view and analyse data from the aquaculture sites in real time. The core of the system will be based on a hub supporting many telemetry protocols for cloud communications, including Cellular, Wi-Fi and Iridium. The wireless hub will support also third-party sensors (e.g. accelerometer pressure tags, biomass monitoring systems, etc.) via its auxiliary sensor port. This technology will enable data-driven ocean farming where knowledge drives better decisions.

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